

Article

From House to Farm: Life Cycle Assessment of Sewage Sludge as a Circular Fertiliser at Regional European Level

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Abstract: This study evaluates the environmental performance of stabilised sewage sludge used as a circular fertiliser across three European regions: Central, Mediterranean, and Northern Europe, comparing its performance against non-renewable fertilisers. The research applies a life cycle assessment approach, considering a mix of the most used stabilisation technologies in each region, such as anaerobic digestion, chemical treatment, thermal drying, composting, and aerobic digestion. Environmental impacts were assessed based on key categories, including climate change, acidification, eutrophication, and resource use. The environmental performance of circular fertiliser production outperformed non-renewable fertilisers in all assessed categories, showcasing its potential as a sustainable alternative. Findings reveal that the choice of stabilisation process is key to the overall environmental performance of the region. High energy-driven technologies such as thermal drying present the bigger impacts. Regional disparities highlight the need for context-specific technology selection to optimise environmental outcomes. The study underscores the importance of integrating energy recovery and nutrient recycling in sludge management practices. These findings advocate for the promotion of circular fertilisers within a sustainable agricultural framework, emphasising technology adaptation based on local conditions to enhance ecological and economic benefits.

Keywords: sewage sludge; circular fertilisers; regionalisation; life cycle assessment; resource recovery; waste valorisation; circular economy

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1. Introduction

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) generate large amounts of sludge as a byproduct of the water treatment process. This sludge is rich in essential nutrients such as nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) and contains significant levels of organic matter, making it a valuable resource for agricultural applications as waste-based fertiliser [1,2].

The use of sewage sludge for agricultural purposes is a widespread practice around the world. In the European Union (EU), it is regulated under Directive 86/278/EEC, which establishes standards to minimise environmental risks by promoting safe application practices and setting limits on contaminants to protect soil quality and ecosystems [3]. However, to maximise benefits and mitigate associated risks, it is essential to ensure proper treatment of sludge prior to its land application [4]. In line with regulatory frameworks, most EU Member States require sewage sludge to undergo stabilisation through biological,

chemical, or thermal processes [5]. However, treatment technologies across the EU 27 vary significantly based on factors such as final disposal methods and the size of the WWTP, which influence the selection of appropriate stabilisation processes [6]. Moreover, significant differences are observed not only between Member States but also within regions of the same country [7].

Transitioning to a circular economy is essential for a sustainable agriculture, as it can significantly reduce dependence on finite resources. Currently, mineral fertilisers are heavily reliant on non-renewable resources like phosphate rock and nitrogen, which are extracted through energy-intensive processes such as the Haber–Bosch method, resulting in significant environmental impacts [8]. Alternatively, replacing mineral fertilisers with circular fertilisers (CFs) derived from waste streams offers several advantages. These alternatives not only supply essential nutrients but also enhance soil structure through their organic matter content [1]. Additionally, the slow nutrient release fosters long-term soil fertility, reducing the need for frequent fertilisation [9]. This contributes to a more sustainable agricultural system and supports the transition toward a circular economy [10].

In this context, the FER-PLAY project aims to facilitate the uptake of alternative fertilisers, protect ecosystems, decrease EU dependence on fertiliser imports, foster circularity, and improve soil health. The project mapped and assessed alternative fertilisers made from secondary raw materials and highlighted their multiple benefits to promote their wide-scale production and use in the field. In this sense, life cycle assessment (LCA) is an appropriate tool used to assess the environmental performance of different products or services [11] and particularly the management of sewage sludge or biofertiliser [12,13]. LCA can support decision-making by guiding the adoption of circular economy practices and ensuring agricultural sustainability through the evaluation of environmental impacts of different alternatives.

This research focuses on the analysis of regionalised sludge stabilisation technologies to enhance representation for specific geographic areas, particularly Europe. The study aimed to demonstrate the importance of identifying the technologies used in each region.

The contribution of this research, in contrast to previous studies, lies in its shifts from site-case evaluation to a global perspective, ensuring geographical coverage of the three selected regions.

To achieve this, the research assessed the environmental performance of circular fertiliser production from sewage sludge using the most common stabilisation technologies in Europe. This evaluation was conducted through an LCA approach, considering three different climatic regions for agricultural applications. The analysis addressed CF production and allowed its comparison with its non-renewable fertiliser (NRF) counterpart. Finally, a life cycle impact assessment was performed to point out environmental hotspots and trade-offs to identify sustainable practices in sludge management across different regions.

2. Materials and Methods

This research conducted an environmental LCA to evaluate the different technologies used for sludge stabilisation in three European regions. The aim was to facilitate the adoption of CF derived from secondary raw materials, promote their wide-scale production, and improve soil health. LCA was performed according to ISO 14040 and ISO 14044 standards [11,14]. The following sections outline the four interrelated stages of the assessment: (i) goal and scope definition, (ii) life cycle inventory (LCI), (iii) life cycle impact assessment (LCIA), and (iv) interpretation of results.

2.1. Goal and Scope Definitions

The main goal of the study was to compare the impacts of producing CF from sewage sludge, excluding its application to soil, in a European context. The regions—Central, Mediterranean, and Northern Europe—were selected based on climatic conditions to ensure comprehensive geographical representation and encompass the diversity of agricultural practices. The countries within each region were selected by the FER-PLAY’s advisory board (Figure 1) based on their expert judgment. Hence, the purpose was to analyse the environmental performance of CF by identifying the most commonly used stabilisation technologies across the three selected regions.

Figure 1. Map showing the EU 27 countries included in the three considered regions (Central, Mediterranean, and Northern).

The selection of stabilisation technology was influenced by various factors such as the size of the treatment plant, influent characteristics, and geographical location [6]. However, although some stabilisation methods are widely adopted, significant variation exists in the technologies used across European countries, with notable differences observed between them. Five sludge treatments were considered:

- Anaerobic digestion aims at reducing, stabilising, and partially disinfecting sludge. It consists of confining the sludge in a reactor at a controlled temperature for a period of time. Typically, mesophilic conditions (around 35 °C) are used, but thermophilic anaerobic conditions can enhance both biogas yield and digestate quality [15]. During this process, biogas (a mixture of methane and carbon dioxide) is generated as a byproduct and is usually used to maintain the temperature of the vessel [16].
- Chemical treatment refers mostly to lime treatment, meaning the addition of lime to sludge in order to raise its pH to 12, destroying or inhibiting the biomass responsible for the degradation of the organic compounds. The treatment also helps with disinfecting sludge, increasing its dry matter content, and making handling easier [16].

- Thermal drying implies delivering energy to the system to evaporate the water, resulting in its densification. A dry matter content of at least 45% is necessary to inhibit the re-growth of bacteria [16].
- Composting is an aerobic process consisting of aerating sludge mixed with a coproduct such as sawdust or animal manure. Composting produces excess heat, which can be used to raise the temperature of the composting mass. The mix then evolves for several weeks. Composted sludge reaches a good level of disinfection and is stabilised, reducing the arising of odours. The final dry matter content in composted sludge can reach over 60%, making it easy to handle [16].
- Aerobic digestion stabilises sludge by degrading the organic matter via microorganisms under aerobic conditions (i.e., in the presence of oxygen). Although a simpler process than anaerobic digestion, it requires a significant amount of energy (from 5 to 10 times more than anaerobic digestion) [16]. As a result, it is mostly used in smaller wastewater treatment plants [6].

The functional unit (FU) has a significant influence on the LCA results; therefore, it is essential to define a suitable FU as a reference unit to which the input and output data are referred [11]. In reviewed studies, such as Lam et al. (2020) and Yoshida et al. (2013) [5,17], the most common FU selected was the volume of treated water, the amount of sludge disposal, or the amount of recovered nutrients. However, this study focuses on comparing the production of a CF with its non-renewable counterpart. Therefore, the selected FU was based on the supply of a specific amount of nutrients to agricultural soils [13]. Specific nutrient supply values for the value chain are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Stabilised sludge nutrient content [16].

Dry matter (% DM)	20.00
Nitrogen content (% DM)	4.11
Phosphorus content (% DM)	2.90
Potassium content (% DM)	0.30

The system boundaries considered in the present work were limited to fertiliser production, starting with the sludge generation (originated from primary clarifier and biological reactor from urban wastewater treatment (UWWT)) and excluding upstream wastewater treatment processes, as depicted in Figure 2. For each stabilisation technology, chemical consumption, energy consumption (i.e., electricity and fuel), and the derived emissions were included. Infrastructure was not considered in the assessment because it was demonstrated in previous studies that only 4% of environmental impacts are attributable to the construction phase [18].

2.2. Data Acquisition and Life Cycle Inventory

LCI was collected for the three European regions. As previously mentioned, the three geographical regions share the same objective and scope, with the unit processes being identical across all scenarios. However, the distribution of stabilisation technologies utilised and the composition of the raw sewage sludge exhibit differences across countries, requiring specific modelling for each case [6]. Therefore, each region has a different LCI. Table 2 presents the distribution of the technological mix, compiled based on the most common stabilisation methods employed in the respective countries of each European region, as outlined in Section 2.1. Further information is provided in Section S1 of Supplementary Material.

Figure 2. System boundaries considered in the study. Urban wastewater treatment was excluded from system limits (dashed lines).

Table 2. Stabilisation method distribution per European region.

Region	Anaerobic Digestion	Chemical Treatment	Thermal Drying	Composting	Aerobic Digestion
Northern	10.8	36.1	39.7	11.6	1.8
Central	39.4	5.3	5.3	15.9	34.0
Mediterranean	68.2	6.0	6.0	6.0	13.7

Primary data at the industrial level were mostly obtained from stakeholders and partners involved in the FER-PLAY project. These data encompassed a wide range of inputs for sludge stabilisation processes, including energy consumption, chemical use, fuel consumption, and waste generation. Conversely, energy and chemical consumption for the necessary unit processes were obtained from secondary sources such as technical handbooks [19]. For the chemical treatment of sludge (i.e., alkaline treatment), the required amount of lime was sourced from the literature [20].

Concerning anaerobic digestion, the production of biogas and digestate, including fugitive CH₄ emissions, was modelled based on the study by Huygens et al. (2022) [20].

Direct emissions linked to biogas combustion were estimated based on the emission factors proposed by the EMEP/EEA air pollutant emissions inventory guidebook [21], taking into account the TIER 1 emission factor. In addition, the composition of the final product and air emissions generated during the compost production process were also modelled based on Huygens et al. (2022) [20]. It was assumed in the composting process that cellulose-rich bulking agents, necessary to combine with sludge during this process, are waste products from other processes and therefore have no associated environmental impact [16].

Secondary data related to energy and chemical production, or waste treatment were obtained from the Ecoinvent v3.9 database [22] by following a “cut off” approach. Meanwhile, the electricity production of each country was obtained from the Eurostat database, considering each country’s contribution to represent the electrical grid of each group of countries. These processes were modelled using background processes for the electricity market. Similarly, NRFs were modelled using a “market” approach representative of Europe. The nutrient supplies from these processes were equivalent amounts provided by stabilised sludge, enabling a comparative analysis of their life cycle impacts.

Table 3 presents the input/output inventories for stabilised sewage sludge for the UWWT value chain, per functional unit, for the Central, Mediterranean, and Northern regions of Europe, respectively.

Table 3. Inventory data for the sludge stabilisation technology mix across the three regions (per FU).

	Central	Mediterranean	Northern	
Inputs from the technosphere				
Materials	Amount	Amount	Amount	units
Raw sludge	3.61	50.57	40.93	t (wet basis)
Electricity	5290.40	2113.62	2136.07	kWh
Polymer (dewatering)	0.23	0.190	0.25	kg
Lime, CaO (chemical treatment)	8.89	9.71	41.30	kg
Fuel (thermal drying)	4.45	4.85	22.71	L
Transportation supplier by truck	0.030	0.025	0.032	tkm
Transportation supplier by train	0.056	0.046	0.060	tkm
Transportation supplier by ship (dewatering)	0.063	0.051	0.067	tkm
Outputs to the technosphere				
Products and coproducts	Amount	Amount	Amount	units
Stabilised sludge	1.00	1.00	1.00	t (wet basis)
Electricity	22.30	260.95	29.38	kWh
Waste	Amount	Amount	Amount	units
Wastewater	7830.00	7700.00	4.96	m ³
Emissions				
To air	Amount	Amount	Amount	units
CH ₄	1.01	0.17	0.16	kg
NO _x	111.09	188.28	27.27	g

Table 3. Cont.

	Central	Mediterranean	Northern	
CO	87.53	146.55	18.16	g
NMVOG	5.61	9.39	1.06	g
SOx (biogas combustion)	6.06	10.15	1.14	g
NH ₃	0.13	0.22	0.024	g
Pb (biogas combustion)	0.0028	0.00050	0.00050	mg
Cd (biogas combustion)	0.0011	0.00020	0.00020	mg
Hg (biogas combustion)	0.067	0.11	0.013	mg
As (biogas combustion)	0.024	0.0340	0.0044	mg
Cr (biogas combustion)	0.10	0.169	0.019	mg
Cu (biogas combustion)	0.17	0.29	0.033	mg
Ni (biogas combustion)	0.13	0.212	0.024	mg
Se (biogas combustion)	0.12	0.20	0.022	mg
Zn (biogas combustion)	2.24	3.76	0.42	mg
PCDD/F (biogas combustion)	0.54	0.90	0.10	ng
Water vapour (thermal drying)	0.050	0.050	0.23	m ³
N ₂ O	22.64	8.641	11.37	g
H ₂ S (composting)	0.010	0.0036	0.0036	g
N (composting)	2.06	0.76	1.03	g
Terpenes (composting)	0.05	0.02	0.02	g

2.3. Assumptions

Sludge generation was considered to have no environmental burdens, aligning with a zero-burden approach. Specifically, all environmental impacts from the wastewater treatment process were attributed exclusively to the main product, treated wastewater, as sewage sludge is considered a waste [23,24]. Consequently, no upstream impacts were assigned to the sludge, as mentioned earlier in Section 2.1.

Aerobic digestion is predominantly used as a stabilisation method in small WWTPs, and it is not even frequently used [6]. For this reason, this technology was disregarded from the study. Regarding the electricity generated from the biogas produced in anaerobic digestion, it is considered a coproduct of the system. Therefore, all the environmental impacts of the process, including the direct emissions from the combustion of biogas, are allocated to the sludge. It is assumed that the electricity generated and leaving the system is free from environmental burdens.

2.4. Life Cycle Impact Assessment

The Environmental Footprint (EF) 3.1. (adapted) method, developed by the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission, was selected to carry out the LCIA. This analysis followed a midpoint approach and included 16 impact categories [25]. However, toxicity-related categories (ecotoxicity freshwater, human toxicity cancer, and human toxicity non-cancer), were not considered in this study due to the lack of robustness and reliability in the characterisation factors [26]. The most relevant categories selected were acidification (A) in mol H⁺ eq.; climate change (CC) in kg CO₂ eq.; marine eutrophication

(MEP) in kg N eq.; freshwater eutrophication (FEP) in kg P eq.; photochemical ozone formation (POF) in NMVOC eq.; resource use, fossils (RUf) in MJ; resource use, minerals and metals (RUM) in kg Sb eq.; and water use (WU) in m³ deprived. These categories were chosen based on previous LCA studies in fertiliser production [12], and they cover environmental burdens on various protection areas, as recommended by PEFRC guidelines [26]. SimaPro 9.6 [27] was the software used to perform the impact assessment. In this study, normalisation and weighting steps were not carried out.

3. Results

This section presents the results of the environmental assessment of CF production across the three regions under study, focusing on the contribution analysis.

Environmental Performance

The contribution analysis of CF production is shown in Figure 3. The analysis reveals a different environmental profile for each region, with environmental burdens being unequally distributed among the different technologies. Differences can be attributed to various factors, such as variations in the composition of raw materials or differing sludge management practices.

Figure 3. Contribution analysis of circular fertiliser for each European region.

In the Central region, the technology based on anaerobic digestion presents the highest contribution in all evaluated categories, except for RUM and RUf, with the following contributions: acidification (50%), climate change (52%), marine eutrophication (67%), freshwater eutrophication (38%), photochemical ozone formation (65%), fossil resource use (20%), and water use (−64%). In contrast, chemical treatment demonstrates a significantly lower contribution across all categories, with contributions not exceeding 17%. Similarly, thermal drying predominantly contributes to the RUf category (37%), while in the other categories, its contributions do not exceed 15%. Composting is mainly responsible for impact categories A (34%), FEP (47%), RUf (31%), and RUM (42%).

When looking at Figure 3, it is observed that the Mediterranean region exhibits environmental benefits in some categories associated with anaerobic digestion, with the contributions of -13% , -74% , -77% , -87% , and -83% for A, FEP, RUF, RUM, and WU, respectively. Anaerobic digestion shows significant impacts in the MEP category; however, its contribution to CC is relatively low (8%).

Regarding the Northern region, anaerobic digestion presents environmental benefits in some categories, such as FEP (-4%), RUF (-9%), RUF (-28%), and WU (-13%). Chemical treatment is the technology with the highest contribution to CC, with an average of 31% in the remaining categories. However, thermal drying dominates all categories, with contributions ranging from 41% to 66%. Finally, the remaining technology exhibits negligible impacts in most categories, except for A, MEP, FEP, and RUM, where its contributions are 16%, 10%, 14%, and 17%, respectively.

4. Discussion

This section identifies the environmental hotspots of the CF value chain, comparing them across regions and with their non-renewable counterparts.

4.1. Identification of the Environmental Hotspots

The environmental assessment identified the hotspots across the life cycle stages for each evaluated scenario. Emissions resulting from combustion of biogas associated with anaerobic digestion represent the main hotspot in A, CC, MEP, and POF for the Central region. These environmental burdens are due to NO_x and sulphur dioxides in A, while methane fugitive emissions contribute significantly to CC and POF. Furthermore, NO_x and CH₄ were significant contributors to MEP and POF, respectively, in the Mediterranean region. Lime consumption during chemical treatment processes also contributed substantially to the environmental burdens in CC for both the Mediterranean and Northern regions. In contrast, fuel consumption in thermal drying is the main carrier across almost all categories for the Northern region.

When comparing the results of this study to previous research, similar environmental hotspots are identified across technologies. For anaerobic digestion, biogas combustion emissions, particularly fugitive methane, are the primary contributors, consistent with the findings of [28,29], especially in terms of global warming. Biogas also provides environmental benefits by replacing grid electricity, reducing fossil fuel consumption and associated SO₂ and NO₂ emissions, thus generating environmental credits for electricity production [30]. Additionally, Houllion and Jolliet (2004) [31] highlighted the significant impact of fuel use for heating, which is also reported in the present study. Similarly, lime has been identified as another key environmental hotspot in chemical treatment processes, emphasising its relevance in impact categories such as CC and POF [32].

4.2. Comparative Analysis of the Scenarios

Figure 4 shows the comparative environmental analysis of the evaluated scenarios among CF production in the three regions with their non-renewable counterparts (absolute values per category are reported in Table S4 of the Supplementary Material). NRF shows the worst performance for all the impact categories assessed due to its high energy consumption during production and the significant environmental impacts associated with the extraction of raw materials.

A lot of LCA studies focused on CF production from sewage sludge. However, when compared to other studies, it is observed that different approaches have been established in the environmental assessment of CF from sewage sludge. Allocation in the production of these fertilisers remains a controversial discussion [33]. Some studies, such as Pradel

et al. (2016, 2019) and Sfez et al., (2019) [33–35], include wastewater treatment within their scope, while others consider not only the production of CFs but also their application to soil [36,37]. Despite the differences in approaches, assumptions, and methodologies, to the best of the authors' knowledge, studies have consistently shown better environmental performance of CF. This highlights the benefits of using sewage sludge as a fertiliser, as well as its potential due to its inherent fertilising properties.

Figure 4. Normalised life cycle impact characterisation results for circular fertiliser production for each European region and its non-renewable counterpart.

When comparing fertiliser production across regions, as illustrated in Figure 4, the technological mix implemented in the Mediterranean region shows the best environmental performance across all categories, with 55% lower impacts in the FEP and RUf categories and reductions of 29%, 21%, and 15% in the WU, CC, and POF categories, respectively, compared to the region with the highest impact. This is mainly attributed to the dominant use of anaerobic digestion technology, where energy recovery is essential in enhancing the overall environmental outcomes.

The Central region exhibits the highest environmental impacts in categories such as A, MEP, and FEP, with increases of 11%, 15%, and 53%, respectively, compared to the region with the best environmental performance in each impact category. This is primarily due to the predominant use of anaerobic and aerobic digestion technologies. However, as noted in previous sections, aerobic digestion was not considered in the study, and thus, the impacts are mostly attributed to anaerobic digestion. In contrast, for categories CC, POF, and RUf, the Northern region shows the worst environmental performance, with increases of 21%, 15%, and 56%, respectively, compared to the region with the lowest impact, which can be attributed to the use of chemical treatment and thermal drying technologies, both of which are equally prevalent. These findings highlight that the results are significantly influenced by the choice of technology implemented in each region.

5. Conclusions

As far as we know, this research is the first environmental analysis of a CF taking a regional approach into account. The results have shown that fertilisers from stabilised sludge have a better environmental performance than their NRF counterparts, highlighting their potential as a sustainable alternative to mineral fertiliser. However, the renewable origin of CFs does not automatically ensure their environmental sustainability, so further studies are needed. Interestingly, the regional approach provides valuable insights. Thus, differences were found among the studied regions, showing that one-size-fits-all solutions are not always the best choice and, therefore, the particularities and nuances of the countries need to be considered before applying a circular solution. The analysis underscores the influence of stabilisation technologies on life cycle impacts, showing the importance of the technology used based on the specific conditions of each region. Stabilisation technologies with resource and energy recovery (such as anaerobic digestion) lead to environmental burden reductions derived from self-generated electricity. Furthermore, the intrinsic properties of CF, such as slow nutrient release and improved adsorption capacity, contribute to reduced impacts during the use phase, promoting soil health and long-term agricultural sustainability. These findings stress the importance of adopting holistic LCA approaches to guide technology prioritisation and support the integration of CF into sustainable agricultural systems.

Supplementary Materials: The following supporting information can be downloaded at: <https://www.mdpi.com/article/10.3390/su17041698/s1>. Table S1. Stabilisation method distribution for the Central region for sludge. Table S2. Stabilisation method distribution for the Mediterranean region for sludge. Table S3. Stabilisation method distribution for the Northern region for sludge. Table S4. Characterisation results of circular fertiliser for each European region per FU. Table S5. Normalisation of characterisation results of circular and non-renewable fertiliser (NRF) for each European region per FU. References [6,38–41] are cited in the Supplementary Materials.

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Data Availability Statement: The original contributions presented in this study are included in the article/Supplementary Material. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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Conflicts of Interest: Authors Jessica Pérez-García, Pedro Villanueva-Rey, Teresa Alvarino and Lucía González-Monjardin were employed by the company Galician Water Research Center Foundation (Cetaqua Galicia), AquaHub-A Vila da Auga. Author Leticia Rodríguez-Hernández was employed by the company VIAQUA, Gestión Integral de Aguas de Galicia, AquaHub-A Vila da Auga. The remaining authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Abbreviations

A	Acidification
CC	Climate change
CF	Circular fertiliser
EU	European Union
FEP	Freshwater eutrophication
FU	Functional unit
LCA	Life cycle assessment
LCI	Life cycle inventory
LCIA	Life cycle inventory assessment
MEP	Marine eutrophication
N	Nitrogen
NRF	Non-renewable fertiliser
P	Phosphorus
POF	Photochemical ozone formation
RUF	Resource use, fossils
RUM	Resource use, minerals and metals
UWWTP	Urban wastewater treatment
WU	Water use
WWTP	Wastewater treatment plant

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